

**THE ROLE OF BRAND AWARENESS IN MEDIATING THE EFFECT OF ELECTRONIC WORD OF MOUTH ON PURCHASE DECISION
(A Case Study of The Originote Products in Gianyar Regency)**

Dewa Agung Ayu Winda Amritaswari¹, I Gst. Ngurah Jaya Agung Widagda K,²

^{1,2} Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Udayana University

E-mail: windaswari9@gmail.com¹

Correspondensi author: Dewa Agung Ayu Winda Amritaswari

Abstract

One of the rapidly growing industries is the personal care and beauty sector, with various facial care brands emerging with different innovations and benefits to attract consumer interest and intention to use their products. Due to the high public interest in self-care and beauty, competition among skincare brands has become increasingly intense. One of the beauty brands in Indonesia that is currently gaining popularity among consumers from various segments is The Originote. In early 2024, The Originote experienced a decline in sales, indicating a decrease in customers' repurchase intention and low public brand awareness of The Originote, which in turn affects purchase decisions. Purchase decision is a process in which consumers begin by recognizing a problem and proceed to making a final decision to purchase a product. This study aims to analyze the role of brand awareness and electronic word of mouth on purchase decision. The sample consisted of 30 users of The Originote products who had purchased the product at least once within a month. The research was conducted in Gianyar Regency. The method used was a survey with a questionnaire technique, analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The results show that Electronic Word of Mouth has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decision, but does not have a significant effect on Brand Awareness. Meanwhile, Brand Awareness has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Decision, but cannot mediate the effect of Electronic Word of Mouth on Purchase Decision. These findings are expected to serve as a reference for future research and provide practical implications, suggesting that The Originote should expand its marketing reach to increase broader brand recognition.

Keywords: Brand Awareness, Electronic Word of Mouth, Purchase Decision

INTRODUCTION

Various new products continue to emerge with unique advantages that differentiate them from competitors. This diversity provides consumers with numerous options when deciding which products to purchase, based on various influencing factors. Along with the increasing needs of consumers, economic actors are increasingly leveraging opportunities to fulfill these demands.

One of the rapidly growing industries is the personal care and beauty sector. Currently, entrepreneurs are introducing care products not only specifically for women's facial and skin care, but also for men, depending on market needs. Numerous facial care brands have emerged with different innovations and benefits to attract consumer interest and intention to use their products. Skincare producers continue to innovate by introducing new formulations, advanced technologies, and natural

ingredients that offer greater benefits. This industry growth is reflected in the high sales of beauty and personal care products on e-commerce platforms.

The high public interest in facial care products is supported by various data indicating increased consumption of beauty products in Indonesia. Based on Databoks (2023), facial care dominates beauty product sales in e-commerce, accounting for approximately 39.4%, making it the largest contributing category. In addition, reports from Statistics Indonesia (BPS) show that public expenditure on personal care and related services has increased annually, reflecting growing awareness of self-care. From an industry perspective, the Indonesian cosmetics market continues to grow, reaching an estimated value of over USD 7 billion in recent years, with an annual growth rate of approximately 5–7%. These data indicate that facial care products have the largest contribution to the beauty industry and are the most demanded category among consumers.

Due to this high demand, competition among skincare brands has intensified, both from local and international brands such as Make Over, WhiteLab, Wardah, Skintific, Emina, Somethinc, and The Originote. This study focuses on The Originote because the brand has gained significant popularity on social media platforms such as TikTok and Instagram and went viral during its initial product launch in 2022. The Originote products, which are halal-certified and approved by BPOM, fall into the premium cosmetic category and are used by various age groups, from teenagers to adults. Its first product was a serum, followed by a moisturizer that received the “Brand Choice Award 2023: Top Moisturizer” from INFOBRAND.ID in collaboration with TRAS N CO Indonesia, indicating strong consumer recognition.

This digital popularity makes The Originote relevant to study in the context of Electronic Word of Mouth (E-WOM), as consumer interactions through the internet can shape purchase intentions. The product also features superior formulations, including hyaluronic acid, ceramide, and chlorella, which provide moisturizing, nourishing, and skin barrier repair benefits, as well as reducing acne and excess oil, making it suitable for various skin types. However, despite its initial virality, The Originote experienced a decline in sales in early 2024 in Gianyar Regency, indicating that brand awareness has not been maximized and affecting purchase decisions.

The study was conducted at Mutiara Permai Cosmetic Store in Gianyar Regency, as this store is an official distributor with complete and accessible sales records of The Originote products. The store serves a diverse range of consumers, allowing the data to accurately represent consumer behavior. Additionally, store staff provided valuable insights regarding sales trends, customer reviews, and purchasing behavior, making it an ideal location for collecting primary data on purchase decisions and brand awareness.

Despite being a local brand that once went viral, The Originote experienced declining sales in early 2024. Initially, sales reached approximately 100 units per month, but later decreased to around 70 units per month. This decline may be attributed to low brand awareness among consumers, which subsequently affects purchase decisions.

The high interest in facial care products is also influenced by changes in consumer behavior in the purchasing decision process. Consumers today tend to actively seek information before making purchases, either through personal experience or through information obtained online. In this context, brand awareness becomes a

crucial factor, as consumers tend to choose familiar and easily remembered brands when faced with multiple options. Furthermore, technological advancements have encouraged the emergence of electronic word of mouth (E-WOM) as a primary source of information influencing consumer perceptions and attitudes. Reviews, recommendations, and user experiences shared through digital platforms can build trust and shape consumer preferences. The combination of strong brand awareness and E-WOM information strengthens consumer confidence, ultimately influencing purchase decisions.

Purchase decision refers to consumer behavior in selecting, buying, and consuming products, ideas, or experiences that best satisfy their needs and desires (Kotler & Armstrong, 2016). This decision involves several stages before the final purchase is made. Consumers are influenced by cultural, social, personal, and psychological factors in making purchasing decisions (Utama, 2014). Therefore, businesses must understand these factors to effectively attract their target market.

Creating the intention to use a product or service is an initial step in marketing, as it determines whether a consumer ultimately decides to use a company's offering (Randi & Heryanto, 2016). Technological advancements have transformed social interactions, including interactions among consumers. Previously, consumer experiences were shared face-to-face, but now they are increasingly exchanged through the internet. This phenomenon is known as electronic word of mouth (E-WOM), which facilitates the exchange of information, opinions, and suggestions regarding consumption experiences (Eriza, 2017).

E-WOM refers to positive or negative statements made by consumers about products, services, or companies, which are shared online for public access (Abubakar et al., 2016). It is considered a credible source of information that can influence purchase intention and decision-making (Luo & Zhong, 2015). The Originote utilizes TikTok and Instagram for marketing, sharing product benefits and skincare education content. E-WOM plays a significant role in generating both positive and negative reviews that can influence potential customers (Jones, 2010).

Brand awareness is a crucial factor in influencing purchase decisions. It reflects how well a brand is recognized and associated with specific products (Hapsari & Sptyawati, 2022). High brand awareness enhances brand recall in consumers' minds, making them more confident in their purchasing decisions.

Previous studies have shown that E-WOM significantly influences purchase decisions, such as research by Prayoga & Mulyandi (2020) and Pratiningsih et al. (2019). However, contrasting findings by Wijaya & Paramita (2014) indicate that E-WOM does not always have a significant effect. Based on these inconsistencies, this study introduces brand awareness as a mediating variable between E-WOM and purchase decisions. Prior research by Suyoga & Santika (2018) supports this approach, showing that brand awareness can mediate the influence of E-WOM on purchase decisions.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study employs a quantitative approach with an associative design aimed at analyzing the relationship between electronic word of mouth as the independent variable and purchase decision as the dependent variable, with brand awareness as a mediating variable among consumers of The Originote products. The research was

conducted in Gianyar Regency, Bali, due to its relatively high economic development and consumer awareness of cosmetic products.

The population consists of consumers in Gianyar Regency who use The Originote products, with an unspecified (infinite) population size. The sample was determined using non-probability sampling with purposive sampling criteria: respondents must reside in Gianyar, have purchased and used The Originote products, and be at least 17 years old. A total of 120 respondents were selected based on multivariate analysis requirements.

Data were collected through surveys using Likert-scale questionnaires (1–5), distributed both directly and via social media and Google Forms. Instrument validity and reliability tests confirmed that all indicators were valid and reliable, with Cronbach’s Alpha values exceeding 0.70. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive and inferential statistics, including path analysis and the Sobel test to examine direct and indirect effects. Classical assumption tests included normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Overview of the Research Object

This study involves individuals residing in Gianyar Regency who use The Originote products. The research aims to examine how brand awareness mediates the effect of electronic word of mouth on purchase decision as the main object of analysis.

The Originote is a halal-certified beauty brand from Indonesia established in 2022. This premium product line is safe and approved by BPOM, making it suitable for teenagers to adult women. The Originote’s first product was a serum launched in March 2022, which quickly went viral. A month later, the brand introduced a moisturizer that further increased its popularity on social media.

According to WanitaIndonesia.co, The Originote received the “Brand Choice Award 2023: Top Moisturizer” from INFOBRAND.ID in collaboration with TRAS N CO Indonesia. The moisturizer provides multiple benefits, including nourishing the skin, repairing the skin barrier, moisturizing, reducing acne, and controlling excess oil. Its key ingredients include hyaluronic acid, ceramide, and chlorella.

Respondent Characteristics

Respondents by Gender

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	68 People	57
Male	52 People	43
Total	120 People	100

Source: Processed primary data, SPSS 2025

Based on the results of primary data processing using SPSS (2025), the majority of respondents are female, accounting for 57%, while male respondents represent 43%.

In terms of age distribution, respondents are predominantly within the 26–34 age group (38%), followed by those aged 18–25 (28%), ≤17 years (18%), and ≥35 years (17%). This indicates that most respondents fall within the productive age group, which tends to have higher levels of activity and mobility.

Furthermore, based on occupation, the majority of respondents are entrepreneurs (48%). Other respondents include civil servants (20%), students (18%), and other occupations (14%). These findings suggest that most respondents have independent professional backgrounds, which may influence their behavior patterns and decision-making processes in the context of this study.

Description of Respondents' Responses

A survey conducted on 120 respondents indicates that the evaluation of research variables is categorized using a score range to measure conditions from very low to very high (Saputra et al., 2019).

The results of descriptive analysis show that the electronic word of mouth variable has an average score of 2.92, brand awareness has an average score of 3.02, and purchase decision has an average score of 3.01. All three variables fall within the moderate category, indicating that respondents' perceptions of these variables are at a moderate level.

Thus, it can be concluded that, in general, respondents perceive electronic word of mouth, brand awareness, and purchase decision regarding The Originote products as fairly good, although not yet optimal.

Results of Analysis

Data Quality Test

Data quality testing is a crucial step in research using questionnaire instruments, aimed at ensuring that the collected data are valid and reliable. This test consists of validity and reliability assessments.

The validity test examines whether the constructs are measured accurately; if not, the construct indicators are considered invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test evaluates the consistency of the questionnaire, meaning that it should yield the same responses when administered to the same respondents at different times. If responses differ under the same conditions, the instrument is deemed unreliable (Sugiyono, 2020, p. 293).

Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics Results

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Electronic Word Of Mouth	120	4	20	11.68	2.990
Brand Awareness	120	4	20	12.08	2.932
Purchase Decision	120	4	20	12.03	2.801
Valid N (listwise)	120				

Source: Processed Primary Data, SPSS 2025

Based on the results presented in Table 2, the following can be explained:

1. The total number of respondents included in the sample is 120.
2. The electronic word of mouth variable was measured across 120 respondents, with a minimum score of 4 and a maximum score of 20. The mean score is 11.68,

with a relatively low standard deviation of 2.990, indicating limited data dispersion.

3. The brand awareness variable has a minimum score of 4 and a maximum score of 20, with an average value of 12.08 and a standard deviation of 2.932, suggesting relatively consistent responses.
4. The purchase decision variable also ranges from 4 to 20, with a mean score of 12.03 and a standard deviation of 2.801, indicating a relatively small variation in responses.

Classical Assumption Tests

1) Normality Test

Table 3. Kolmogorov–Smirnov Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		Unstandardized Residual	
N		120	
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000	
	Std. Deviation	2.43677670	
	Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.051
		Positive	.045
		Negative	-.051
Test Statistic		.051	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}	
a. Test distribution is Normal.			
b. Calculated from data.			
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.			
d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.			

Source: Processed Primary Data, SPSS 2025

The results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test show an Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value of 0.200. Since this value exceeds 0.05, it can be concluded that the residual data in the regression model are normally distributed.

2) Multicollinearity Test

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test Results

Model	Coefficients ^a	
	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
1 Electronic Word Of Mouth	.989	1.012
1 Brand Awareness	.989	1.012

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision

Source: Processed Primary Data, SPSS 2025

The multicollinearity test results indicate that there is no multicollinearity in the regression model, as all variables have Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values below 10 and tolerance values above 0.10.

3) Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 5. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.684	.839		3.200	.002
1 Electronic Word Of Mouth	-.051	.046	-.102	-1.106	.271
Brand Awareness	-.014	.047	-.028	-.300	.765

a. Dependent Variable: Abs_RES

Source: Processed Data, SPSS 25

The multicollinearity test results indicate that there is no multicollinearity in the regression model, as all variables have Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values below 10 and tolerance values above 0.10.

Path Analysis

Path analysis is an extension of multiple linear regression used to examine both direct and indirect relationships among variables (Ghozali, 2021).

1) Effect of Electronic Word of Mouth on Brand Awareness

Table 6. Linear Regression Model 1 Results

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.107 ^a	.011	.003	2.928

a. Predictors: (Constant), Electronic Word Of Mouth

Source: Processed Data, SPSS 26

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	13.311	1.082		12.301	.000
1 Electronic Word Of Mouth	-.105	.090	-.107	-1.171	.244

a. Dependent Variable: Brand Awareness

Source: Processed Data, SPSS 26

The constant value of 13.311 indicates the level of brand awareness when electronic word of mouth is zero. The regression coefficient of -0.105 indicates a negative relationship, meaning that an increase in electronic word of mouth is associated with a decrease in brand awareness by 0.105 units, assuming other variables remain constant.

However, the model has very weak predictive power, as indicated by an R Square value of 0.011 and an Adjusted R Square of 0.003. This implies that only 1% of the variation in brand awareness is explained by electronic word of mouth, while the remaining 99% is influenced by other factors not included in the model.

2) Effect of Electronic Word of Mouth and Brand Awareness on Purchase Decision

Table 7. Linear Regression Model 2 Result

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.493 ^a	.243	.230	2.458

a. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Awareness, Electronic Word Of Mouth
 b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision
 Source: Processed Data, SPSS 26

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	4.535	1.372		3.305	.001
1	Electronic Word Of Mouth	.443	.076	.472	5.840	.000
	Brand Awareness	.193	.077	.202	2.494	.014

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision
 Source: Processed Data, SPSS 26

The constant value of 4.535 represents the purchase decision when the independent variables are zero. The coefficients of 0.443 and 0.193 indicate that electronic word of mouth and brand awareness both have positive effects on purchase decision.

This means that an increase in each independent variable leads to an increase in purchase decision, assuming other variables remain constant. However, the model's explanatory power is relatively weak, with an R Square value of 0.243, indicating that only 24.3% of the variation in purchase decision is explained by the model, while 75.7% is influenced by other variables

3) Effect of Electronic Word of Mouth on Purchase Decision with Brand Awareness as an Intervening Variable

Figure 1. Path Analysis Results

Legend:
 ————— : Direct Effect
 - - - - - : Indirect Effect

Source: Processed Data, SPSS 26

Hypothesis Testing (t-test)

Table 8. t-Test Results for Purchase Decision as the Dependent Variable

Model	Coefficients ^a			t	Sig.
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	4.535	1.372		3.305	.001
1 Electronic Word Of Mouth	.443	.076	.472	5.840	.000
Brand Awareness	.193	.077	.202	2.494	.014

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision

Source: Processed Data, SPSS 25

1. Effect of Electronic Word of Mouth on Purchase Decision

The t-test results show a t-value of 5.840 with a significance level of 0.000. Since this value exceeds the critical t-value (1.65798) and the significance level is below 0.05, the hypothesis stating that electronic word of mouth has a positive and significant effect on purchase decision is accepted.

2. Effect of Brand Awareness on Purchase Decision

The t-test results show a t-value of 2.494 with a significance level of 0.014. Since this value exceeds the critical t-value and the significance level is below 0.05, the hypothesis stating that brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on purchase decision is accepted.

Table 9. t-Test Results for Brand Awareness as the Dependent Variable

Model	Coefficients ^a			t	Sig.
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	13.311	1.082		12.301	.000
1 Electronic Word Of Mouth	-.105	.090	-.107	-1.171	.244

a. Dependent Variable: Brand Awareness

Source: Processed Data, SPSS 25

3. Effect of Electronic Word of Mouth on Brand Awareness

The t-test results show a t-value of -1.171 with a significance level of 0.244. Since the significance value exceeds 0.05, the hypothesis stating that electronic word of mouth has a significant effect on brand awareness is rejected.

Sobel Test

The Sobel test was used to examine the mediating role of brand awareness. The results show a t-value of -1.02 with a significance value of 0.139, which is lower than the critical value (1.65798). Therefore, brand awareness is not proven to mediate the effect of electronic word of mouth on purchase decision, and the corresponding hypothesis is rejected.

Coefficient of Determination Test

Table 10. Coefficient of Determination Test Results (Model 1)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.107 ^a	.011	.003	2.928

a. Predictors: (Constant), Electronic Word Of Mouth

Source: Processed Data, SPSS 26

Based on the test results above, the R Square value is 0.011 (1%). This indicates that the electronic word of mouth variable explains only 1% of the variation in brand awareness, while the remaining 99% is explained by other variables not included in this study.

Table 11. Coefficient of Determination Test Results (Model 2)

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.493 ^a	.243	.230	2.458

a. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Awareness, Electronic Word Of Mouth
b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision

Source: Processed Data, SPSS 26

Based on the test results above, the R Square value is 0.243 (24.3%). This means that electronic word of mouth and brand awareness jointly explain 24.3% of the variation in purchase decision, while the remaining 75.7% is influenced by other variables outside the scope of this study.

Discussion

The findings of this study are strongly supported by previous research indicating that electronic word of mouth has a positive and significant effect on purchase decision. Information shared by other users is generally perceived as more credible and capable of enhancing consumer trust in making purchasing decisions. Studies by Liyono (2022) as well as Apriliani and Setyawati (2023) also emphasize that informative and engaging digital content can directly encourage consumers to purchase products.

However, the finding that electronic word of mouth does not significantly affect brand awareness is consistent with the study by Andrea and Keni (2021), which suggests that brand awareness is more influenced by visual elements and branding strategies rather than consumer reviews.

Furthermore, the significant effect of brand awareness on purchase decision is supported by research conducted by Permata et al. (2023) and Ikhyia'Ulumudin and Wahyuati (2021), which state that consumers tend to choose well-known brands as they are perceived to be safer and more trustworthy.

Meanwhile, the inability of brand awareness to mediate the relationship between electronic word of mouth and purchase decision is also in line with findings from Gabriella et al. (2022) and Rozaq (2025), which indicate that the influence of e-WOM on purchase decision tends to be more direct rather than mediated.

Thus, this study not only reinforces existing theories but also highlights that other factors, such as personal experience and consumer preferences, may play a more dominant role in determining purchase decisions.

CONCLUSION

This study examines the role of brand awareness in mediating the effect of electronic word of mouth on purchase decision for The Originote products in Gianyar Regency. Based on the results of the data analysis, several conclusions can be drawn:

1. Electronic word of mouth has a positive and significant effect on purchase decision.

The more positive and credible the e-WOM received by consumers, the stronger their purchase decisions and their tendency to buy the product or service offered.

2. Electronic word of mouth has no significant effect on brand awareness.

The increase in online feedback or electronic word-of-mouth communication does not necessarily enhance consumers' recognition or recall of the brand.

3. Brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on purchase decision.

The stronger the consumer's ability to recognize and recall a brand, the higher the likelihood of making a purchase decision.

4. Brand awareness does not mediate the effect of electronic word of mouth on purchase decision.

Although consumers receive information or recommendations through e-WOM, this does not significantly enhance brand awareness in a way that influences purchase decisions.

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